

PROFESSIONAL SKILLS FROM LITERATURE

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Abstract. *This article discusses the study of the image of the mind in Uzbek literature. In addition, the role of the image of the mind in the literature is emphasized.*

Keywords: *image, literature, soul, spirituality, faith, genre, poetry.*

ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫЕ НАВЫКИ ИЗ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается изучение образа ума в узбекской литературе. Кроме того, подчеркивается роль образа разума в литературе.*

Ключевые слова: *образ, литература, душа, духовность, вера, жанр, поэзия.*

The poet's heart listens to the world ...

(Maksud Shaikhzoda)

A person with a pure heart, with a broad outlook, the ability to think deeply can only do good. Literature speaks of goodness, elegance, purity, beauty. The main object of literature is a person, which means that he has so much responsibility that the role of the creator in society, in the fate of a person, especially in educating young people, as a creator of spiritual treasures is extremely important. By the way, as the President of our country Islam Karimov noted, "Spirituality and enlightenment have always been the strongest feature of our people for many centuries" (1).

Today, when the spirituality of young people is relevant, it is necessary to repeatedly turn to the work of young writers so that buds of respect for the history of their people and the glorious past grow in the hearts of the younger generation. It became one of the most important tasks, for example, the education of ideal people.

In the hearts of the young generation, reading works imbued with the national idea and ideology of independence, attention to the past of their ancestors is growing, because today "... the incomparable spiritual heritage of our great ancestors, our thousand-year history, we have returned to our culture and language, our national customs and traditions, in a word, all the riches of human spirituality are restored. (2)

The struggle for the independence of the homeland, the freedom of the nation, the expression of human freedom has been a priority in literature of all times. These themes are the essence of the artistic and aesthetic research of the poetess G. Askarova, who embodies the symbol of nationalism in his works.

Indeed, patriotism is a national feeling that arises from the attitude of each nation to its homeland, spiritual, cultural and moral values created by its people. This is a manifestation of a certain form of thought in the psyche, in the mind of a person. In these aspects, it is advisable to consider the cycle of poems of the poet "Vatan dei yuksalar ruhim".

Patriotism, manifested in the character of the lyric heroine of poetry G. Askarova, is associated with human freedom, freedom of the Motherland, values, independence of the Motherland. Rather, it manifests itself in the form of an appeal, persuasion, appeal, lyrical monologue, heartfelt appeals in the spirit of journalism. In particular, in his poem "The Bride's Dream": I keep my baby awake Wake up, I say, Indeed, the search for answers to the

questions posed by time and social reality, the desire to fully express the spiritual world of contemporaries, the growing interest in the history of nationalism, the deep expression of philosophical observations, patriotism, populism in the verses of Gulzhamol Askarova. .` are colored expressions of poetry.

We are faced with a completely unconventional interpretation.

Indeed, if the younger generation is brought up in the spirit of love for the works created by their ancestors, centuries-old traditions, national values, it is natural that they are influenced by works expressing national identity. The poet impresses with his observation. Depicting the human image in art, he certainly captures the world of the protagonist, above all the inner world, subtle feelings.

The peculiarity of the poet's art of poetry is that it creates a picture of various experiences, adding social, philosophical, aesthetic content to the details of life. The confirmation of these ideas is reflected in the following verses:

Father, the pain of poetry woke me up
The color of the horizons touched my heart.
El's gentle word raised me
The sadness of the nation made me a man ...
If one day my soul rises as a Motherland,
When I say people, I mean exactly that.
Father, do you remember me?
In memory of the Motherland O`

Yes, G. Askarova's poems are very polished, rich in sincere feelings, colorful in themes, freedom achieved in public life, free-thinking echoed in her soul.

The deeper the poet understands the realities of life, the more responsible he becomes for his works. He strives with all his heart for freedom, strengthening independence, kindness and beauty.

Its lyrical protagonist is an Uzbek woman who actively fights for her destiny and burns with love of life. The essence of G. Askarova's poems is an artistic and aesthetic concept that perfection, spirituality is one of the factors that determine human happiness.

Human happiness, the guarantee The psyche of a struggling woman is skilfully drawn artistically. The fate of the unfortunate woman is at the center of the poet's work: of individual freedom, is one of the most important means of spiritual beauty. The psyche of a struggling woman is skilfully drawn artistically. The fate of the unfortunate woman is at the center of the poet's work:

I'm a bad girl, I'm a vengeful girl
Is this my generation of swords ?! ...
I swear not to leave a loan
I'll take cash.

The true desire of the lyrical hero is to see the nation freely, not to lose the independence of the Motherland, the unity of the Turkish nation. Therefore, indifference and indifference, unconsciousness worries about what can happen to the nation:

I know that happiness means -
This is either my humiliation or my violence.
Nazokatim - from nigokhim-u,

My breath is my ugliness.

The problem of freedom of the nation, freedom of the people, which is the idea of the lyric hero created by the poet, is inextricably linked with the personal happiness of a person. After all, true happiness should be manifested in its completeness and integrity. Apparently, the lyrical heroine of G. Askarova is proud, self-confident, but at the same time rather bold and simple by nature. Sometimes they resemble a magnificent landscape painted by an artist, but sometimes there are poetic interpretations of life events. All this suggests that the poet's mind is rich in poetic observations, he can express his thoughts without undue silence through symbols and symbols. The number of works on historical themes in Uzbek literature, which is included in the treasury of world literature, is growing. In the near future, Uzbek prose will change its character, embracing reality in all its complexity and reflecting it in its own way, in its direction and contradictions. Most importantly, he synthesized the image of epic reality with the image of the psyche of the characters. In other words, the strengthening of the image of the psyche in the epic narrative, that is, the reflection of reality through the analytical depiction of the psyche of the characters, testifies to the growing development of psychodogism in modern Uzbek prose. It should be noted that the natural, unique combination of epic, lyrical and dramatic imagery in this process was due to the enrichment of the techniques and means of revealing the psyche of the characters more deeply, reasonably and convincingly.

The rise of the writer Assad Dilmurod in the field of spiritual images is associated with his deeper analysis and interpretation of the spiritual world of man as a writer and as a person. It is inevitable that a certain situation, a certain behavior and a certain mood will not always be the same in a person's activities. In a number of his works, the artist proved that this confidence is replaced by extraordinary, unpredictable situations and actions. At first glance, such cardinal changes in the human psyche seem to contradict the logic of the characters, but a thorough artistic analysis of their inner world, all the contradictions in the psyche leaves no room for the above-mentioned paradox, because the image of the psyche serves as evidence. As you know, writing a historical work has its own difficulties. Especially famous scientists, such as Abu Raikhan Beruni, Pahlavon Muhammad, Amir Temur, Sultan Hussein Baikaro, bear great responsibility for the life and work of the commanders before the creator, the historical and political environment in which they lived. , and, in general, scientific works. they are created. requires a lot of imagination. "Pahlavon Muhammad" Assad Dilmurod is somewhat imperfect in its composition due to the multifaceted conflict and its focus on the contradictions between a number of his characters. But if you look closely, it is easy to see that interpersonal contradictions in it are expressed through a variety of mental images. Comparing the psyche of the characters in certain contradictions, that is, using the parallelism of images to describe the struggle between them, the writer Pahlavon Muhammad and other works try to clearly and convincingly reveal the heroes. Naturally, in this way, the main character is the main character, and the events of the work are often evaluated through the eyes of the characters. The main character has a complex character, he assesses each event or person through his own thoughts, through psychological analysis. For this reason, from the very first pages of the work, the writer turns to memory, which has risen to the level of the favorite method of depicting his psyche. This protagonist analyzes the past, every step he takes, and the people he knows, he knows, with whom he communicates. At the same time, this common thought process allows characters to enter the plot one at a time.

In conclusion, in the verses of the poetess Gulyamol Askarova, special attention is paid to the analysis of the psyche, the description of the mood of the lyric hero.

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